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Research Article

**PRINCIPLES AND ELEMENTS OF THE SYSTEM IN THE
MANAGEMENT OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF
THE REGION.****Polina Shmygaleva¹, Olga Shatalova², Elena Kashcheeva², Anna Kobeleva²,
Olga Bruzhukova³.**

¹Stavropol branch of Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration, Lermontova str., 189, Stavropol 355000, Russia., ²North Caucasus Social Institute, Goleneva str., 59a, Stavropol 355000, Russia., ³Southern University (Institute of Management, Business and Law), Nagibina ave., 33a/47, Rostov-on-Don 344068 Russia.

Article Received: January 2019**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

The article presents the essence and content of the socio-economic development of the region, defines the relation of the definition of "effectiveness" to the social sphere. In addition, the authors consider the main indicators of the economic development of the region, systematized and supplemented the principles of socio-economic development of territories, etc.

Keywords: *system management, socio-economic development, region, principles, elements.*

Corresponding author:**Polina Shmygaleva,**

Stavropol branch of Russian Presidential Academy,
National Economy and Public Administration, Lermontova str.,
189, Stavropol 355000, Russia.

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INTRODUCTION:

The essence of regional social development is to provide social guarantees, designated by the federal center, in an effort to improve the quality and standard of living of the population. Such an interpretation of the understanding of the essence of regional social policy, of course, does not cover all aspects of the social development of territories, however, the concept of "social sphere" is so broad that it is in itself a subject of multidimensional research [3].

The main elements of the social sphere can be identified: the standard of living of the population of the region, the social sector (culture, health, education) and the environmental component.

The content of the social block of regional management is a set of measures aimed at the effective implementation of social processes in the studied area.

A separate emphasis is placed on the concept of "efficiency", which can be considered from the standpoint of the ratio of the sizes of key indicators of the social sphere of regional development compared to the amount of budget funds invested [2]. The main objects of this block will be the population itself, social infrastructure and social institutions. In the process of further detailing and concretization of the study by descending to a separate regional system, we will define groups of regional development indicators for each block of the social and economic sphere, the dynamics of which will be an indicator of the effectiveness of regional socio-economic policies.

Separately, it is necessary to dwell on the concept of "social institutions", which is understood to mean the form of organizing social interaction between people (the family institution has a demographic aspect; sociocultural institutions; the institutions of religion, etc.).

Social institutions provide for the organization of the interaction of people's livelihoods in terms of meeting the social, economic, political, cultural or other needs of society as a whole or part of it.

One of the main sources of social financing is tax collection (both regional and federal), in connection with which such a mechanism, such as tax, is allocated by us separately.

It should be noted that the social and economic spheres are closely interconnected by themselves and interdependent, since the economic sphere is the source of funding for all social projects, and the

successful implementation of social policies (in terms of increasing employment, for example) will subsequently provide additional revenues to regional and federal budgets.

The content of the economic block is a set of measures aimed at the effective implementation of economic processes in the region. As in the social block, the concept of "efficiency" becomes a priority, however, unlike the social block, the economic sphere does not directly depend on budget allocations, but on the contrary, is itself a producer of social resources, creating a regional product. Since, in addition to the public sector, there is an enormous share of enterprises with private and share capital in the region, the concept of efficiency in relation to regional policy can be viewed from the standpoint of increasing the competitiveness of a particular territory in a single economic space.

As an object of the economic block, we have defined the regional economic system, which includes the branches of tangible and intangible production, the production infrastructure, as well as the available production and economic resources in the region.

The main indicators of the economic development of the region are: increased investment attractiveness; increase resource efficiency; increasing productivity and expanding production; development of economic infrastructure; increasing the competitiveness of regional products and services [4].

A distinctive feature of the socio-economic policy of the region is its close interconnection and interrelation with the macro level. In fact, the so-called "super-system connections" are most pronounced here, when the regions themselves are system formations and enter a higher level system (state-wide), forming a super-system [5].

Considering the regional economic development, it should be noted that this is such a comprehensive concept that it will need further specification of its constituent blocks: budget, tax, credit, investment, production, agricultural, etc.

Regional socio-economic development is based on the application of a system of principles that determine, by definition, its effectiveness and rationality in relation to the available internal resources and invested funds [1]. On the basis of the conducted research, the author established the interdependence of the federal and regional levels of socio-economic development, therefore, it is necessary to differentiate the principles of its

functioning depending on the chosen level.

In addition, an additional classification of the principles of socio-economic development is

necessary in terms of their basic content and the addition of existing functions (Table 1).

Table 1: Principles of socio-economic development of territories

Macro level	Regional level
Main	
1. Principle of polarized development	11. Principle of encouraging regional initiatives
2. Principle of synergy	12. Principle of innovation
3. Principle of differentiation	13. Principle of consistency
4. Principle of globalization	14. Principle of self development
5. Principle of the sovereign economy	15. Principle of development of competitiveness
Complementary	
6. Principle of coordination	16. Principle of balance
7. Principle of partnership	17. Principle of efficiency
8. Principle of subsidiarity	18. Principle of optimality
9. Principle of additionality	19. Principle of stabilization
10. Principle of concentration	20. Principle of adaptability
Providing	
21. Principle of planning	
22. Principle of monitoring and control	
23. Principle of prospects	

In our study, the territory of the Russian Federation as a whole was singled out as a macro level, the level of an individual subject of the country was chosen as the regional level (in our case, the Stavropol Territory). The so-called meta-region, which is the federal district of the Russian Federation, may occupy an intermediate position in this classification. However, since the principles of the macro level are more inherent to him, it does not seem necessary to single out it separately.

The group of basic principles of socio-economic development of the macro level include:

1. The principle of polarized development. The essence of this principle stems from the main goal-setting of the overall "development strategy of the Russian Federation until 2030 - raising the standard of living of the population and ensuring economic growth" [2]. Getting this result is possible only on the basis of rational and optimal use of all available resources in the country. Since different territories have different internal resources, the division of social production is designed in such a way as to satisfy the domestic needs of the country to the greatest extent and ensure its competitiveness in the external market. Thus, in the strategic development programs of the country, the priorities and development tasks of each region are determined depending on its participation in the overall production process of the country.

2. The principle of polarized development. The essence of this principle stems from the main goal-setting of the overall "development strategy of the Russian Federation until 2030 - raising the standard of living of the population and ensuring economic growth" [2]. Getting this result is possible only on the basis of rational and optimal use of all available resources in the country. Since different territories have different internal resources, the division of social production is designed in such a way as to satisfy the domestic needs of the country to the greatest extent and ensure its competitiveness in the external market. Thus, in the strategic development programs of the country, the priorities and development tasks of each region are determined depending on its participation in the overall production process of the country.

3. The principle of synergy provides for strategic single-vector development of the entire territory of the country depending on the chosen goal setting. This effect is achieved through regulatory and administrative impact on the development of individual subjects of the country, that is, the availability of development programs based on the overall concept of the country's development.

4. The principle of differentiation. This principle is a logical continuation and at the same time interdependent (as well as the entire system of principles of socio-economic development of the

country), along with the principle of polarized development [3].

5. The principle of globalization. The formation of this principle is especially important under the influence of external pressure on the Russian Federation, which is caused by the introduction of economic and political sanctions after foreign policy transformations in the Russian Federation in 2014.
6. The principle of sovereignty of the economy. The logical continuation of the principle of globalization is the process of sovereignty of the national economy, which is achieved exclusively by increasing the country's security from external influence [4]

The group of basic principles of the regional level of socio – economic development is a kind of continuation of the mark-level principles, but they include principles that are more specific to the regional segment and can be implemented depending on the regional component [2]. One can disagree with this opinion of the author, if we say that even a separate country or group of countries in a global context can also be considered as a region. However, at the beginning of the study, the object and subject of work were identified, and therefore we consider the macro level as the Russian Federation as a whole, and the region of the Russian Federation, the Stavropol Territory, is defined as the regional segment. At the same time, we focus on the fact that the classification of principles given in Table 2 is universal and can be transferred (mainly its content) to other objects of study.

The group of regional principles of socio-economic development of the region includes:

1. The principle of encouraging regional initiatives. The action of this principle correlates with the principle of macro-synergy and is its logical continuation. The essence of this principle lies in the fact that all subjects must equally be provided with the “budgetary” attention of the federal center, but the directions for spending these funds should be determined by the initiative of regional authorities. In this aspect, budget funds should play a stimulating function, encouraging the regions to self-development and ensure economic growth.
2. Another principle of the regional bloc is the principle of innovation. Some researchers argue that at present almost the entire economic system in the Russian Federation is based on the application of innovative methods [4] and, thus, this principle can relate to the

macro level, however, in our opinion, innovativeness is too individual a process that allows developing targeted growth centers, the definition of which is the exclusive prerogative of the regional authorities. It should also be noted that innovation is currently used not only in the economic sphere, but also inherent in all social processes.

3. The principle of consistency. The action of this principle is based on the general provisions of the strategic development of the Russian Federation, as a result of which the actions of the regions, even under the condition of independent initiative development, regional authorities should coordinate with the federal authorities, primarily in the area of spending and control over the use of allocated budgetary funds [1]. Ensuring in practice this principle leads to an improvement in overall socio-economic stability throughout the entire territory of the Russian Federation.
4. The principle of independent development. The very definition of a region as an object of research suggests that this territory has its own unique internal factors and conditions of functioning, the study of which determines the general trajectory of its development. Today, regions are free to make final decisions based on the results of their development trajectories if they provide a nationwide positive effect. At the same time, the conditions of rationality, objectivity and priority of socio-economic development should be applied.
5. The principle of development of competitiveness involves ensuring competitiveness not only of products produced in a given territory, but also ensuring the competitiveness of the region itself in conditions of limited budgetary investment resources [2]. Currently, there are many programs of subsidiary support from the federal authorities for the development of one or another regional segment, but in order to receive such preferences, it is necessary to interest the center and provide guarantees of obtaining a positive effect, both economic and social.
6. Characterizing the group of basic principles of socio-economic regional development, it is necessary to disclose the essence and specifics of the complementary principles, the need for which is due to a more detailed specification of the separation of functions and actions of the level authorities.

To the complementary principles of the macro

level are the following:

1. The principle of coordination. The essence of this principle lies in the fact that the federal authorities, after the adoption of legal documents regulating the general socio-economic development of the country, in the future as applied to the regions, coordinate their actions on internal development by defining a common development trajectory, constant monitoring and monitoring, and need counseling. In this case, we are not talking about the complete inaction of the regions in this process in terms of the independence of development, however, given the centralization of budget financing, the final decision is always the prerogative of the federal authorities.
2. The principle of partnership ensures the parity of the development interests of both the whole country and its individual subject. The main task is to protect the interests of all stakeholders and participants with the goal of optimal interaction. The partnership can be considered in all areas, from the rule-making, taking into account the interests of the development of individual territories, and ending with the controlling. The partnership should also manifest itself in the process of developing, monitoring and evaluating the implementation of regional socio-economic development programs.
3. The principle of subsidiarity. The definition of this principle as a supplement is due to the fact that the management functions of federal and regional authorities should be clearly regulated and separated in order to increase the development efficiency of the entire socio-economic system. In this case, it is about the possible delegation of some functions to another level, if this is required by the condition of optimality and rationality of the social and economic policy.
4. The principle of complementarity. The essence of this principle comes from the fact that the regions in their assets have their own funds, formed from the replenishment of regional budgets. The complementarity is manifested in the fact that the funds allocated by the federal center for regional development should not replace regional funds, but complement them, that is, there is a cross-action of the principles of subsidiarity and complementarity.
5. The principle of concentration. The effect of this principle is determined by the limited budgetary resources, therefore, in order to increase the efficiency of the use of the latter,

the support of the federal center should be targeted and specific, not diffuse. World experience shows that such a concentration on certain points of growth always gives a nationwide positive effect, and the return of invested resources is a fundamental criterion.

The complementary principles of the regional level of socio-economic development include the following:

1. The principle of balance. The content of this principle is based on the fact that on the part of the federal authorities, absolutely all regions and territories should be provided with the conditions that allow them to perform regional functions and tasks in the field of socio-economic policy.
2. The principle of efficiency. This principle is defined in the group of regional due to the fact that the initial efficiency is formed at the micro level, starting from a specific business unit. Thus, in our system under study (region - country), primary efficiency will be formed at the regional level, and overall federal efficiency can be assessed using integral indicators.
3. Approximately the same condition determines the inclusion in the regional bloc and the principle of optimality, the essence of which assumes that all programs of socio-economic development are based on the main criterion - how to do better for a region or country. The principle of stabilization. Stability is the main characteristic of the socio-economic development of territories. Stability is characterized as a positive process of development of socio-economic systems, expressed in the constant steady growth of the main indicators of development.
4. The principle of adaptability. The attribution of this principle to the regional is also quite controversial. This is due to the fact that, based on the experience of the development of the national economy of the Russian Federation, starting from 2014 (the period of global transformations), the macro level had to constantly adapt to the new economic conditions. However, insisting on the inclusion of this principle in the regional bloc, we proceed from the fact that the regions primarily feel the impact of global transformations on themselves.
5. Having considered the block of the complementary principles of the macro level and the regional level, we propose a combined block of principles ensuring the functioning of

the two previous blocks. The commonality and the absence of the need to divide this block into a macro level and a regional one is due to the fact that their implementation is necessary progressively, by step-by-step action at all levels.

This group of principles includes the following:

1. The principle of planning. Realization and effective functioning of socio-economic development are possible only on the basis of strategic planning programs, which provide for both strategic goal-setting and tactical corrective actions aimed at ensuring the effectiveness and efficiency of programs already implemented in the form of insurmountable influence factors. Plannedness is necessary, first of all, for the distribution of the state's available resources for a long-term period in order to optimize them and ensure efficiency.
2. The principle of monitoring and control. The introduction of this principle is an objective consequence of the position that the socio-economic development of both a country and its separate part should be effective in relation to the invested funds. Constant monitoring of the main indicators of the socio-economic development of the territories ensures the timely identification of any negative deviations in the plans and allows you to make corrective tactical decisions. The control functions are entrusted to the federal authorities and partially transfer their powers to the regional authorities.
3. The principle of prospects. This principle is based on the fact that any implemented programs of socio-economic development imply their fixed ending, expressed not only in the actual temporary end of their action, but also in achieving the intended goals expressed by specific indicative indicators. Perspectivity is evaluated not only from the standpoint of the forecast scenarios for the achievement of these indicators, but also from the standpoint of resources expended, which can be determined on the basis of factor analysis.

CONCLUSION:

Thus, having considered the main factors and conditions for the formation and development of socio-economic development in the level aspect, in a paragraph, it is possible to optimize on the basis of them, methodical approaches to organizing and evaluating the effectiveness of prospective (strategic) management of the region.

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